

Use of Generative Artificial Intelligence in Undergraduate Assessment

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1 Use of Artificial Intelligence

The use of Artificial Intelligence is *not* prohibited. The use of Large Language Models (LLMs) such as OpenAI’s ChatGPT GPT-4 (paid), Perplexity.ai (free/paid), Microsoft Copilot in creative mode (free), or Claude 3 Opus (paid) when working on this assessment is permitted. These tools can complement your efforts on assessments and can assist with planning, research, and editing, but they *must be used intentionally and with utmost care*. Intentional and careful use of these tools may assist the quality of your final submission, but poor or reckless use of the tools can quite easily negatively impact the quality of your submission. **You are fully responsible for any issues or errors arising from their use.** If you are considering actively engaging with LLMs to assist in completing this assessment, then please read the following very carefully.

1.1 Acknowledgement

It is essential to acknowledge any tool used, both the model used and the way that you used it. (See below for my acknowledgement.)

1.2 CRITICAL: Confabulations, hallucinations, and fictitious sources

It is your responsibility to use Generative AI tools ethically and appropriately. **Any fictitious sources contained in your submitted paper will result in a failure of the assessment, regardless of whether they originated from your own research, Generative AI, or a random webpage.** This is not an academic integrity issue, but a matter of ensuring the accuracy and reliability of your work.

Remember, LLMs always sound confident but are not always correct (and depending on how the LLM is used may be very wrong). Proper prompting is essential for improving the quality of the results (see below for resources on prompting).

1.3 Embedded models

Microsoft Word and Google Docs have built-in text autocomplete features powered by LLMs. Use this "autocomplete" feature at your own risk, as it may result in bland and generic writing.

1.4 Vague responses

Poor prompting may lead to American-centric or vague responses that do not address the specifics of Australian law. When using these models, it is your responsibility to thoroughly check all outputs to ensure they are relevant and accurate. Reliance on an LLM output without thorough oversight is strongly advised against.

1.5 Copyright concerns

As future lawyers, it is your responsibility to obey the law. Do not upload copyrighted material, including unit materials (slides, articles, question text) or anything with a clear copyright, to these international systems without an appropriate license (e.g., CC-BY). Always read and comply with the terms of use of any research services you use.

1.6 Appropriate and ethical use

Read the terms of service of the LLM tools you use. Some, like OpenAI (<https://openai.com/policies/sharing-publication-policy>), have specific acknowledgement requirements for your work.

While powerful, these tools may not always increase productivity or research speed (<https://www.hbs.edu/faculty/Pages/item.aspx?num=64700>). Use them judiciously.

2 A trap

Do not treat LLMs as search engines. Even those with web search capabilities (e.g., perplexity.ai, ChatGPT GPT+ subscription, Microsoft Copilot) may not search effectively. Ensure that all factual information you want the models to work with is well-contained within your prompts.

3 Recommendations

We strongly advise against using ChatGPT's free version, as it may lead to unsatisfactory results and is prone to confabulations. Use tools running GPT-4 or equivalent, such as Microsoft Copilot in creative mode (free with a throwaway account, not your MQ account). Avoid upsells from the LLMs and choose "creative mode" for GPT-4; "balanced mode" uses GPT 3.5.

Here are recommended sources to help you use these powerful but potentially dangerous tools:

4 Bibliography

A short bibliography on prompting for those who are interested.

- <https://www.oneusefulthing.org/p/a-guide-to-prompting-ai-for-what>
- <https://www.oneusefulthing.org/p/captains-log-the-irreducible-weirdness>
- <https://simonwillison.net/2023/Apr/2/calculator-for-words/>

5 Acknowledgement

Claude 3 Opus was used to edit this text on AI usage to remove many of the Americanisms introduced by my colleague.

6 Changelog

2024-04-04: Document typeset in L^AT_EX. Prepared for general distribution. CC-BY applied.